

OPTIMIZATION OF A CRUCIFORM COMPOSITE SPECIMEN UNDER BIAXIAL LOADING BY MEANS OF EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS

E. Lamkanfi^a, W. Van Paepegem^a, J. Degrieck^a, A. Makris^b, C. Ramault^b and D. Van Hemelrijck^b

^aGhent University, Department of Materials Science
Sint-Pietersnieuwstraat 41, B-9000 Gent, Belgium

^bFree University of Brussels, Department of Mechanics of Materials and Construction
Pleinlaan 2, B-1050 Brussels, Belgium

Ebrahim.Lamkanfi@UGent.be

SUMMARY

In this paper a newly developed algorithm based on evolutionary strategies is presented for the optimization of a composite specimen under biaxial loading. Starting from a general geometry with a specific lay-up, the strain is increased significantly in the central zone which is necessary to characterize the material in biaxial (fatigue) loading.

Keywords: *Evolutionary Strategies, Optimization, Cruciform, Biaxial Loading, Fatigue*

INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, many studies have been performed on the biaxial testing of composite materials. Several geometries have been developed in this regard, such as tubular specimens and cruciform geometries, to obtain failure in the biaxially loaded zone. However, this appeared not to be a simple task. An algorithm, based on the principles of the evolution theory of Charles Darwin and first developed by Rechenberg [1], has been used to find an optimal geometry where damage starts in the central zone. First, the initial geometry which triggered the authors to develop the algorithm is briefly explained. Also the issues that came up while testing this initial geometry, with a very specific material and stacking sequence, are discussed to offer the overall view why and how the geometry is optimized. Furthermore, the evolutionary algorithm is explained, together with its two most important operators, i.e. the mutation and the recombination operators. Also the use of the finite element method in the optimization scheme is highlighted briefly. Finally, the obtained numerical results are shown and compared with similar geometries used as reinforcement in concrete plates in the region of the supporting columns.

CRUCIFORM SPECIMEN

The composite material used in this study is a glass epoxy manufactured by LM Glasfibre (Denmark) using the RTM technology. This composite, which is widely used in the wind turbine industry for the construction of rotor blades, has a $[(\pm 45/0)_4/\pm 45]$ stacking sequence. The cruciform geometry, in which this lay-up is used, is shown in

Fig. 1. where one group of $[\pm 45/0]$ is milled away at each side of the specimen in the centre of the laminate. This leads to a laminate with a thickness of 6.57 mm in zone 1 and a thickness of 3.59 mm in zone 2. Besides the change in thickness, which is applied to obtain higher strains in the central zone, also some attention should be paid, in the light of the optimization process that will be discussed later on, to the fillet corners, consisting of two rounding radii, an inner and an outer radius, which are also used to lead the incoming load to the central zone. It appeared from a recent study, conducted by the authors, that these geometrical adaptations to a purely cross shaped specimen, make it difficult to develop a biaxial stress state in the material. It was therefore concluded the geometry itself has a significant influence in obtaining a biaxial loading state and that an optimization of the geometry became imperative. Therefore, a numerical optimization scheme is developed where the composite material is optimized for a maximum strain in the central area. Moreover, due to the large number of optimization variables, such as the corners radii, the milled thickness and the biaxial load ratio, the more robust evolutionary strategies are chosen in comparison with the traditional optimization methods, such as the gradient methods.

Figure 1 : The geometry of the cruciform specimen with the dimensions and the stacking sequence.

EVOLUTIONARY STRATEGIES

Evolution strategies (ES) are stochastic optimization methods based on the theory of Charles Darwin. These strategies, developed by Rechenberg [1] and Schwefel [2] in the seventies of the past century, were in the beginning commonly applied for continuous optimization problems. In the nineties Thierauf and Cai [3] proposed a modified ES algorithm to handle also discrete problems. These stochastic methods differ from the conventional optimization algorithms by using randomized operators such as the mutation and the recombination operator which are crucial in the optimization of the cruciform specimen. Apart from these two operators, many other parameters can be adjusted for a better performance of these algorithms. However, only the recombination

and mutation operator will be explained here, whereas more detailed information about the other parameters can be found in comprehensive works such as those of Schwefel [4] and Bäck [5]. But before going into these operators, a short overview is given of the optimization process that is used in this study. This will also highlight in which order the operators are applied on the parameters in the optimization process and how the descendants of the parents are obtained and survive to a next generation.

Optimization process

As explained before, evolutionary strategies are mainly steered by operators which are indissoluble related with the evolution theory of Charles Darwin. Their function and the way they operate in the full survival cycle are depicted in Fig. 2. First a begin population, consisting out of a series of parental models, is initialized, meaning that each parent is characterized by a set of parameters that are stored in its genes. In the case of a composite specimen, these are the geometrical parameters. Once initialized, a new set of descendants is obtained through modification of this genetic information by means of the recombination and mutation operators. These adjustments in parameters can be easily understood as small changes in the geometry of a biaxial loaded composite specimen, leading to new but slightly different geometries. Hereafter, an appropriate fitness value is attributed to all the individuals through finite element calculations. It is important to mention here that the criterion that is chosen to determine the potential survival rate of an individual will have a significant influence on the final result. For this is a specific criterion must be chosen that expresses in a nominal way how one individual performs better than another one. In our case, we have opted for the ratio of the maximum ϵ_{xx} strain outside the central region to the one in the central region. Once this fitness value is obtained, a selection procedure is started where only the best individuals are allowed to pass to the next generation. Finally the evolution loop is terminated and the new children take the role of the parental models over in the next generation.

Figure 2: Schematic of the evolutionary loop.

Recombination operator

Evolution strategies allow the application of different types of recombination mechanisms. These operators can work on two as well as on different individuals from a population. In the first case, the term asexual operator is used for the recombination whereas in the second case the operator is called the pan-matic operator, which has no biological basis. In the sexual form, the recombination operators are applied on two arbitrarily chosen individuals from the parental population, where the choice for two similar individuals is not suppressed. In case of the pan-matic recombination operator, one individual is arbitrarily chosen from the parental population and afterwards fixed. For each position of the parameter vector of this fixed individual, a new individual is chosen from the parental population with who the recombination is executed. In other words, for the creation of one descendant, all individuals from the parental population can be involved.

Recombination is always used in evolutionary strategies for the creation of all descendants in the case where the number of parents μ is greater than one. The different traditional recombination-operators are called discrete and intermediate recombination. Both mechanisms exist in the sexual as well as in the pan-matic form. In the case of the discrete recombination each vector component is arbitrarily copied from the corresponding component of one of the two parents. Intermediate recombination indicates that the components of the descendants are obtained by taken the arithmetic average of the corresponding components of the both parents. The intermediate recombination is often extended to a more generalized form where instead of taking an average value, a weight factor χ is introduced (χ in $[0,1]$) as a uniform distributed random variable. When χ appears under the form of χ_i , leads to the fact that for each value of i a new χ_i -value is generated. In the case χ has no index, a single value is taken for the creation of a descendant. Consequently, two additional recombination types are obtained.

For the two-dimensional case, the different possibilities for recombination are depicted in Fig. 3. Here, P_1 and P_2 indicate the positions of the two parental individuals. By means of discrete sexual recombination, only the corners of the rectangular (marked with 1 in the figure) can be reached. Intermediate sexual recombination between the two parents results in the middle of the diagonal of the rectangular as descendant (2). The generalized version of the intermediate sexual recombination can lead to descendants which are located along the diagonal of the rectangular (3). Finally, the generalized intermediate pan-matic recombination allows the descendant to be produced everywhere inside the rectangular (4). It is clear that, by means of the recombination, the n -dimensional hyper body formed by the parental population can be never abandoned by a descendant. This shows that the recombination operator leads to a volume reduction of the hyper body, which accelerates the search process in a significant way.

Figure 3 : Possible recombination types in a two dimensional space.

Mutation operator

The mutation-operator is considered to be an arbitrary, purposeless manifestation that occurs very rarely. If such a mutation is interpreted as a sum of many small individual manifestations, it is then logic to assume that the chance on the occurrence of a mutation will correspond to a probability function that leads to small changes which are more frequent than larger ones. Therefore, a binomial distribution is considered for discrete variations, whereas for continue variations a Gaussian or normal distribution is chosen (Fig. 4(a)). With this, two conditions should be fulfilled: (i) the mean value ξ of each component z_i is 0 and (ii) the applied variation on these components σ^2 is also small. The probability function for a normal distributed random event z_i is given by

$$p(z_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_i}} \exp\left(-\frac{(z_i - \xi_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right)$$

and can be understood for a two parameter optimization problem as a possible region where the descendant can be found after the application of the mutation operator. This can be observed in Fig. 4(b).

Figure 4: Normal and binomial distribution (a) and the representation of the mutation operator in a two dimensional space (b).

RESULTS

In the following section an evolutionary strategy is presented where 2 parents are taken as the initial population from which 3 descendants are created. The initial population is obtained by applying small adjustments from an initial geometry shown in Fig. 5(a). This is done to have also some diversity in the initial population, which is assumed to be the case in each (organic) population. In order to test the applicability of the evolution strategy, the initial geometry is taken as a simple flat composite specimen with a lay-up identical with the one considered in Fig. 1 but without a milled central region. This is done to investigate the performance of the evolution strategies in its basic form, without any additional complications. After application of the recombination and mutation operator, the parameter vector of each of the individuals is translated in a finite element model. After assigning the appropriate fitness value, the optimum is obtained and shown in Fig. 5 where the ϵ_{xx} strains are depicted for respectively the initial (a) and final (b) geometry. It is seen that the highest values are shifted from the edges of the specimen in Fig. 5(a) to the central zone of the specimen in Fig. 5(b). This indicates that the evolutionary strategy is capable of making the optimization process to evolve to a geometry where the ϵ_{xx} strain is forced to be higher around the central region compared with the one found outside this region. However, the existence of four lobes around the central section is not realistic and also not favourable. This can be deduced by the almost zero strains in these lobes which actually means that the algorithm is isolating these regions with almost no load bearing function into four zero stress-strain regions. Because we have chosen here for an optimization scheme where the coordinates of one quarter edge of the specimen are able to vary freely in the x- as in the y-direction and where each point on this geometry edge should remain in this quarter region, the existence of the formation of the four lobes is made possible through the close gathering of these points. Therefore, these four lobes attached to central area should be cut out from the specimen. Besides this, the optimum in Fig. 5(b) should also be adjusted at the arms for the clamping of the specimen in the biaxial test set-up. Despite of these adjustments, the evolution strategy gives in any case an enhancement of the maximum strain ratio of 4 to 1.2. This means that where in the initial geometry the ϵ_{xx} strains was

4 times larger outside the central region in comparison with the one in the centre, in the optimum case this ratio is still only 1.3.

Figure 5 : Initial geometry (a) evolving to the final optimal geometry (b).

This indicates that the evolution strategy is capable of evolving to a cruciform specimen that will perform better in the achievement of a biaxial stress state despite of the shortcomings discussed before. This can be observed in the comparison of Fig. 6(a), where the lobes are removed from Fig. 5(b), with the cruciform geometry in Fig. 6(b). The latter geometry can be found in the literature as a reinforcement of concrete plates above the region of the supporting columns [6]. This is not a conclusive comparison but just an indication that the evolutionary algorithm is able, after some program adjustments in the parameters, to obtain an optimal geometry. The comparison can not be performed on an exact scale, also because of the fact that no milled out area is considered in the finite element models, whereas in the real geometry of Fig. 6(b) the milled out area is clearly observable. Therefore, some adjustments in the evolutionary algorithm are necessary to first rule out the lobe formation automatically and secondly to implement the possibility to have composite individuals with a milled area.

Figure 6 : Optimized geometry used as reinforcement in concrete plates in the region of supporting columns : a numerical (a) and experimental (b) result.

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